

SPHERE

Spectro-Polarimetric High-contrast Exoplanet REsearch

ParanalScienceOperations

Julien H. Girard

SPHERE Instrument Scientist

Presentation of SPHERE

Its many modes, fantastic capabilities

Calibration Plan

Various types of calibrations, various goals => **choices**

Status & problems (often) encountered

Almost 2 years of regular operations, improved smoothness

Focus on IRDIS DPI: push the limits

Accurate high-contrast imaging polarimetry

Towards characterising exo-planetary atmospheres through polarimetric direct imaging

PRESENTATION OF SPHERE

Talk by D. Mouillet
on High-Contrast Imaging

CALIBRATION UNIT

IRDIS

ZIMPOL

IFS

selection of FP1 sources or FP lamp
focalization of the distortion grid or not

Differential tip-tilt sensor
focalization of FP3 source

visible coronagraphic

visible Lyot Stop

Polarization compensator1 - PCOM rotation

Calibration slide

Slide with 2 amici prisms

Slide to focus IFS camera

Piezo stage for dithering

FLC Modulator Delay ON/OFF

WSSF SMALL
WFS spatial filter

WFSW WFS density wheel

IFS pupil lens translation stage

IFS Lyot stop wheel

IFS mirr

LAMPS

shutter

ND_1.0

PRI_YJ

-15.2

IFS Detector

Cryostat

Bartoli

Callas

DM Deformable Mirror

AOFM

ATM3 1592.1

CFSL2

CPAW

Apodizer wheel

IADC

AUTO

VADC

AUTO

ZISL MIRR

CFSL3

OPEN

VCW

CFOC4

CFSL4

VLW

CLEAR1

FP4_2

OPEN

OPEN

ZIFW0

ZHRT

NWP-2

ZIFW1

N_R

ZIFW2

N_R

ZITT5

ZITT3

ZITT4

ZITT1

ND_4.0

ZCRT

ZHRT

FLCM

N_R

N_R

DM

Selection Calibration @ FP2

CPPTW

rotation of HWP1

H1RT

PTTM Pupil Tip-Tilt mirror

CPPW

OPEN

HZRT

Image tip tilt mirror

ITTM

TM2

TM1

De-rotator

CPRT

NOM

GRID

OPEN

CFSL1

CGSL

CFOC

CPSH Entrance Shutter

LAMP

GREEN

LASER

CBEFW

OPEN

FP1_NIR

to PS-VIS

to PS-NIR

to PS-K

to FP2

to FP3

to FP4

CBSL2

IR coronagraphic wheel

ICW

OPEN

IR ND wheel in CP

CPFW

ND_3.5

IRSL

DIC_H

Full Block Lyot stop, prism grism

IRLW

IRFW1

B_HBB filters

DB filters

IRFW2

Polarizers

D_H23

Pupil Imager

IFDS

IFS

IFS camera

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MODES OF SPHERE

	IRDIS	(IRD)IFS	ZIMPOL
Modes	(C) I DBI DPI LSS SAM (P100)	IFS (EXT) SAM (P100)	(C) I DPI SAM (P100)
Spectral range/ Resolution	0.95-2.32 μm	0.95-1.65 μm	500-900 nm
Field of View	11"x11"	1.7"x1.7"	3.5"x3.5" Mosaicing not yet offered
Rotator options	Pupil-stabilized (default) Field stabilized		Static (P1) Field-Stabilized (P2)

FIELD(S) OF VIEW OF SPHERE

FIELD(S) OF VIEW OF SPHERE

IRDIS

HR8799 b
falls out
of IFS FoV

SPHERE'S CALIBRATION PLAN

Types of Calibrations

Static (long-term monitoring, maintenance / health check)

Dynamic (calibrate science data, QC0, Cal4Cal, can also feed HC)

Internal (usually daytime)

Flats, Darks, Backgrounds, etc.

On-sky (usually nighttime)

Examples: Photometric Standard Stars, Astrometric fields, etc.

AO / Common Path Calibrations (IQ, Coronagraph centering)

Special Calibrations (e.g. User Provided, specific to a project)

Various Goals

Provide calibrations to users, including archive users

Generate “Science Grade” Data Products

Maintain/improve immediate and long-term performances

Push specific performances, explore/characterise new mode/capability

Choices!

So many modes and combinations

A vibrant, competitive community

Discussions!!!

DATA CHAIN & QC0

Science Case/Idea **USER**

Simulate performances

Design OBServations

Set of constraints
versus knowledge/measurement
of the atmospheric conditions

QC grade can depends on
Instrument Health
behaviour versus (many parameters)

ETC/Manual

Choose appropriately

Perform / Classify (QC0)

Deliver Observations

ESO/SciOps

Analyse & Publish
or perish...

Archive

CALIBRATION PLAN: COMPLETENESS

CAL SPHERE calChecker: calibration completeness monitor

Last update: 2017-01-16T08:50:34 (UT) [?] [Old 00h:18m ago] [?] [?] Paranal date*: 2017-01-15 [?] server: www.eso.org HQ HELP ASSOC-RULES DETAILS

Last header: SPHER. 2017-01-14T08:45:23.413.hdr [?] [transfer] [?] [ngas] [?] *Date on this monitor changes at 21:00 UT. Refresh frequency: 10hr day and night

General news: Long-term calibrations and maintenance [complete overview](#) / [how to execute](#) [?]
 SPHERE news: all long-term calibrations within validity range

HC refresh analyze ISSUES mark BAD QUALITY HELP DATA ASSOC-RULES history... contact monitors: DataTransferMonitor | BandWidth

science calcal [?] Product availability depends on the data transfer to Garching and the archive access there (check the "transfer" and "ngas" flags above!)

DATE*	2017-01-09	2017-01-10	2017-01-11	2017-01-12	2017-01-13	2017-01-14	2017-01-15	LOST?	Calibration action?	Setup:
<small>(color if science data acquired)</small>	report NLT	no data NLT	no data NLT	<small>(may require CR)</small>	<small>(take these data types ...)</small>	<small>... for these setups</small>				
Raw CAL displays:	CRW	no raw files	no raw files							
Product quality:	products	no products	no products							
Data types:										
Setup:										
IRD_SCI_CL OPEN_B_Ks_ST_ALC2_CLEAR_12.0000000			OK				no data (yet)		OK	
IRD_SCI_DB ND_1.0_B_H_ST_ALC2_D_H23_4.0000000			OK						OK	
OPEN_B_H_ST_ALC2_D_H23_16.0000000				OK					OK	
OPEN_B_H_ST_ALC2_D_H23_32.0000000					MISS <small>(not yet analyzed)</small>			RD_BACKLIRD_DARK		OPEN_B_H_ST_ALC2_D_H23_32.0000000
OPEN_B_H_ST_ALC2_D_H23_64.0000000				OK					OK	
IFS_SCI ND_1.0_YJ_16.0000000			OK						OK	
OPEN_YJ_16.0000000				OK					OK	
OPEN_YJ_32.0000000					NOK <small>(not yet analyzed)</small>			ESLBACKLIES_DARK		OPEN_YJ_32.0000000
OPEN_YJ_64.0000000				OK					OK	
ZPL_SCI_IMG OPEN_CntHa_N_Ha_Standima			OK						OK	
OPEN_N_R_N_R_Standima				OK					OK	
ZPL_SCI_P2 ND_1.0_Cnt820_Cnt748_FastPol					OK				OK	
OPEN_B_Ha_CntHa_FastPol			OK						OK	
OPEN_Cnt820_Cnt748_FastPol					OK				OK	
OPEN_CntHa_B_Ha_FastPol					OK				OK	
OPEN_CntHa_CntHa_FastPol					OK				OK	
OPEN_V_N_R_FastPol			OK						OK	
OPEN_V_V_FastPol					OK				OK	

www.eso.org/observing/dfo/quality/SPHERE/reports/CAL/calChecker_SPHERE.html

MONITORING: HEALTH CHECK

SPHERE: IRDIS_CI counts in brightest flat (last 90 days)
QC data range: 2016-10-18 ... 2017-01-11*

Talk by W. Hummel (Xshooter)

powered by QC: www.eso.org/HC

created by trendPlotter v3.6.2 on 2017-01-15T22:36:18

GENERATING SCIENCE DATA PRODUCTS (SDP)

+ **EVENTUAL
CAL
"S" (SKY)
FRAME**

**SPECIFIC TO SPHERE
(PIPELINE)**

www.eso.org/sci/software/pipelines/

SPHERE OPERATIONS STATUS

History

Commissioning June 2014 - December 2014 (4 runs)

Science Verification (calibrate science data, QC0, Cal4Cal, can also feed HC)

GTO (marginally started during commissioning, fully started in February 2015)

General Operations, including Service mode: P95 - April 2015 (nearly 2 years!)

Productivity

57 accepted/published Refereed Papers!

1 new planet detected (Wagner et. al 2016), many new disks in scattered lights, “other science”

Operations “smoothness”

SPHERE is mostly operated by 1 astronomer and/or one Telescope/Instrument Operator (TIO), “SciOps 2.0” is effective thanks to a simple QC0 scheme and

Still, many things remain to be improved

Better astrometric calibrations, information (WCS in headers)

QC0 based on contrast, aligned with Exposure Time Calculators (ETCs)

Performance analysis, correlations with atmospheric parameters, RTC data, predictions

Non-Common Path Aberrations NCPA mitigation: improve contrast

Low Wind Effect mitigation

Etc.

Discussions!!!

DAYTIME CALIBRATIONS EXAMPLES

Daytime calibrations for IRDIS

Calibration	Modes	Matching parameter(s)	Validity
Background	all	DIT	1 day
Lamp Flat	all	Filter	1 day
Distortion map	all except IRDIS_LSS	Filter, Coronagraph combination	1 week
Wavelength calibration	IRDIS_LSS	Slit/Grism combination	1 day

Daytime calibrations for IFS

Calibration	Modes	Matching parameter(s)	Validity
Dark	all	DIT	1 day
Lamp Flat	all	Prism	1 week
Wavelength calibration	all	Prism	1 week
Spectra registration	all	Prism	1 day
Distortion map	all	Filter (+dichroic), Coronagraph combination	1 week

DAYTIME CALIBRATIONS EXAMPLES

Daytime calibrations for ZIMPOL

Calibration	Modes	Matching parameter(s)	Validity
Bias	all	Readout mode	1 day
Dark	all	DIT, readout mode	on request
Imaging flat	all	Filter (+dichroic), readout mode, focal plane mask on substrate (if used)	1 day
Polarimetric flat	ZIMPOL_P1, ZIMPOL_P2	Filter (+dichroic), readout mode, focal plane mask on substrate (if used)	1 day
Modulation efficiency	ZIMPOL_P1, ZIMPOL_P2	Filter (+dichroic), readout mode	1 day

NOTE: ZIMPOL distortion maps are taken weekly in V, N_R, N_I for monitoring purposes.

COMPLEXITY, TRADE-OFFS, CHOICES

Observing mode	Comments	Service/Visitor mode
IRDIFS	- Pupil-stabilized (default) or Field stabilized - Coronagraph: ALC_YJH_S	S+V
	- 4QPM and other coronagraphs - NGS R > 11 mag	V
IRDIFS_EXT	- Pupil-stabilized (default) or Field stabilized - Coronagraph: ALC_YJH_S	S+V
	- 4QPM and other coronagraphs - NGS R > 11 mag	V
IRDIS_DBI	- Pupil-stabilized (default) or Field stabilized - Coronagraph: ALC_YJH_S, N_ALC_Ks with K-band filters	S+V
	- 4QPM and other coronagraphs - NGS R > 11 mag	V
IRDIS_CI	- Pupil-stabilized (default) or Field stabilized - Coronagraph: ALC_YJH_S, N_ALC_Ks with K-band filters	S+V
	- 4QPM and other coronagraphs - NGS R > 11 mag	V
IRDIS_LSS	Long Slit Spectroscopy in LRS and MRS	(S*)+V
IRDIS_DPI	Differential Polarimetric Imaging	S (BB_J only) + V
ZIMPOL_P1/P2	- Derotator: P1 (static) or P2 (Field-Stabilized) - Filters: combination of NB and BB filters not allowed - WFS/ZIMPOL splitter: GREY or DIC-HA - No coronagraph (allowing some saturation) or V_CLC_M_WF - Some saturation allowed - Detector/modulator: FastPol, SlowPol - Field-Position: on-axis	S+V
	- Other coronagraphs - NGS R > 11 mag - NB and BB filter combination	V
ZIMPOL_I	Same as P1/P2 but with readout mode StdImaging.	S+V
	- Other coronagraphs - NGS R > 11 mag - NB and BB filter combination	V

Many
modes
OK

Many
Combinations

Coronagraphs
Including Lyot stops
Filters

Difficult
Long Calibrations

PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED (EXAMPLES)

Astrometry: derotator positioning accuracy

True North calibration

Installation of a “TIM-board” for better time reference

Distortion grids not used (large separation candidates)

IRDIS Dual-band polarimetry

HWP control law

(cross-talks, bad polarisation efficiency)

QC0 with ZIMPOL

Short Wavelengths

Large Strehl (peak flux) variations

Low Wind Effect (LWE)

Affects Good seeing data

Is NOT seen by RTC (AO system)

FUTURE: COMBINATION OF TECHNIQUES/ MODES

HDS+HC

Combining high-dispersion spectroscopy (HDS) with high contrast imaging (HCI)

RIAUD & SCHNEIDER+ 2007

SOON POSSIBLE @ VLT/UT3

SPHERE

+

CRIRES+

+

EXPRESSO

LOVIS+ 2016

FOCUS ON IRDIS/**DUAL** BEAM **POLARIMETRIC IMAGING (DPI)**

ROB **VAN HOLSTEIN** & JOS **DE BOER**

VAN HOLSTEIN+ 2017

DE BOER+ 2017

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE SPHERE/IRDIS/DPI MODE

POLARIMETRIC EFFICIENCY / ACCURACY

HWP CONTROL LAW

CROSS-TALKS & INSTRUMENTAL POLARIZATION

SPHERE/IRDIS/DPI MODE POLARIMETRIC DIFFERENTIAL IMAGING

SPHERE/IRDIS DPI MODE

DE BOER+ 2017

POLARIMETRIC EFFICIENCY (DATA)

POLARIMETRIC EFFICIENCY (2D)

POLARIMETRIC EFFICIENCY (1D)

TW HYDRA: SCATTERED LIGHT IMAGE & EARLY RESULTS

TW Hya in HST/WFPC2
Krist et al. 2000

TW HYDRA: ALMA

Andrews et al. 2016
Band 7 -- 870microns
beam 24 x 18 mas

Tsukagoshi et al. 2016
Combined Band 4 + 6
Beam 72 x 47 mas

TW HYDRA: SCATTERED LIGHT WITH SPHERE

H-band, polarised intensity,
Image scaled by R^2 , FWHM 40mas

Data obtained as part of the SPHERE GTO programme

DETECTING POLARIZATION OF PLANETARY-MASS COMPANIONS?

Characterizing exoplanets: from intensity...

DETECTING POLARIZATION OF PLANETARY-MASS COMPANIONS?

CURRIE+ 2013

MAROIS+ 2008 ... ZURLO+ 2016

INSTRUMENTAL POLARIZATION

NEW DPI RESULTS FROM SPHERE

Gallery, courtesy of H. Avenhaus (2016 -)

DE BOER+ 2016

MORE TO COME!

EXTRA SLIDES

POST-PROCESSING TECHNIQUES

Following Talk by D. Mouillet on High-Contrast Imaging

MILLI+ 2016
(INCL. GIRARD, ACCEPTED)

LOCI: linear combination of images to minimize the noise

LAFRENIÈRE+ 2007

PCA : orthogonalisation of library of images that is restrained to the first modes

SOUMMER+ 2012
AMARA+ 2012

Sparse Decomposition / **Low rank** approximation

GOMEZ+2016 (PREP)

RDI WITH LARGE PSF LIBRARY

PCA: PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS

Large PSF DICTIONARY from survey

HIPXXX: NACO L-band

MAWET+2016

telescope efficiency x2 (SURVEYS!!) => **Strategy for Girard et al. L' filler survey**

BETTER "AO" CALIBRATION

Before correction

After correction

ZELDA

ZERNIKE WFS

INSIDE SPHERE/IRDIS

Before correction

After correction

N'DIAYE+2016

ACTION ITEM

FOR THE "PAC"

(MARCH 2017)

SPHERE SAM "PRE-COM"

CHEETHAM,
GIRARD+ 2016 (SPIE)

HD 142527B

SPHERE SAM: ASTROMETRY!

